

Ankara University

Faculty of Science
Department of Astronomy and Space Sciences

Degol Cad. TR-06100, Tandogan, Ankara - TURKEY
Tel: +90-312-2126720/1312, Fax: +90-312-2232395

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To Whom It May Concern,

I hereby confirm that Dr. Tobias C. Hinse has been acting as an external scientific co-advisor for my MSc student Ekrem Murat Esmer during the period 2014 - 2015. The MSc thesis title is "Exoplanet Discovery in Multi-Stellar Systems with the Timing Technique" and was successfully defended in June 2015 at Ankara University, Turkey.

Prof. Dr. Selim O. SELAM

Ankara University, Faculty of Science
Dept. of Astronomy and Space Sciences
Tel: +90 312 2126720 ext:1364, Fax: +90 312 2232395
e-mail: selam@science.ankara.edu.tr
WEB: http://science.ankara.edu.tr/~selam/index_eng.html